

DEVELOPMENT OF WRITING SKILLS FOR TEACHING ENGLISH IN SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Annotation: The article presents an analysis of the historical foundations of the development of writing teaching skills, considers an integrated approach as a leading approach to teaching foreign languages, and provides an overview of active and interactive teaching methods. Written speech is considered as a creative communicative skill, understood as the ability to express one's thoughts in writing. Secondary school acts as the second stage, where the foundations of communicative competence are laid and continue to develop, allowing for the implementation of foreign language communication and interaction of children, including with native speakers, at an elementary level.

Keywords: communicative competence, written speech, exercise, method, computer technology.

Language skills are formed only in speech and there is no other way to master the language at the present stage. Most of the potential of the language lies in writing, the role of which in teaching a foreign language is great, as it allows you to save language and phonetic knowledge, serves as a reliable thinking tool, stimulates speaking, listening and reading in a foreign language. P.K. Babinskaya, I.L. Bim, I.D. Galskova, N.I. Gez, E.N. Weiner studied the problems of formation of communicative competence in teaching writing, A.R. Luria, B.T. Likhachev, R.P. Milrud and many others.

The purpose of the study is to identify the most effective methods of forming communicative competence in teaching middle-level students writing in English.

Theoretical foundations of the development of writing skills

Communicative competence is the ability to carry out speech activity by means of the studied language in accordance with the goals and situation of communication within a particular sphere of activity [8, p. 6]. The purpose of teaching writing is the formation of students' written communicative competence, which includes the possession of written signs, the content and form of a written work of speech. The level of formation of communicative competence in writing depends not only on the level of proficiency in a particular foreign language, but also on the general level of education of the writer, since the basis is the general ability to work with information.

With the transition from the lower grades to the middle grades of school, the position of children in the system of business and personal relationships with other people changes. In adolescence and adolescence, the process of cognitive development is actively underway. At the middle stage, the center of gravity in writing is transferred to spelling and writing is developed as a means of contributing to the formation of oral skills. Teenagers and young men can already think logically, engage in theoretical reasoning and introspection. A characteristic feature of adolescence is the willingness and ability to many different types of learning, both in practical terms (work skills) and in theoretical terms (the ability to think, reason, use concepts) [5, p. 144]. In middle school age, shifts in memory development are most significant. It is adolescence that makes qualitative changes in the structure of memory.

The "average performance" of memory increases to 14 years. At the age of 15, a decline in memory development begins: at this age, it is lower than at 14-year-olds.

All methodologists have similar opinions and cite identical goals and skills that a student should have at the end of the basic course.

Skills that a student should possess:

- to inform a foreign friend about yourself, your family, school, city, your interests and hobbies;
- request information about the same from your addressee;
 - write a note/letter to a newspaper or magazine, observing the norms accepted in the country of the studied language;
- provide basic personal information in the questionnaire /form;
 - make working notes after reading the printed text (make a plan, write out keywords, etc.) in order to further use them in a written statement [4, p. 47].

The most significant difficulties that arise during the learning of writing:

- the process of learning writing is constantly complicated by discrepancies between the sound and graphic planes of expression of thought in a foreign language;
 - if during oral communication something can be omitted by the speaker, filled in by facial expressions, gesture, intonation, then when communicating in writing, the statement should be specific and complete, as detailed as possible in order to fulfill its communicative function;
 - the lack of the ability to expressively intonate one's speech requires a more careful selection of syntactic means, and the lack of the ability to use facial

expressions and gestures requires a more rigorous grammatical design of written speech;

– the formation of skills in the field of the graphic and spelling system of the studied language, the presence of such features as unreadable letters, homophones, changeable forms of grammatical spelling, which manifest themselves only in writing and do not entail a change in the sound form of the word;

– mastery of written speech presupposes the presence of a certain level of socio-cultural competence in the student [9, pp. 125-126].

Perception, memory, attention, and thinking are of great importance in learning a foreign language, which determine the success of educational activities.

Teaching writing at the middle stage of learning English

Exercise as a means of teaching foreign language speech always has a purpose, it is characterized by a special organization, and it is always aimed at perfecting the way of performing an action. Each exercise has certain qualities. Nowadays, the problem of developing written exercises and creating a whole system of written exercises interacting with certain oral exercises remains very important and relevant. By and large, writing training is based on three series of exercises:

1. Exercises aimed at the formation of graphic and spelling skills that orient in writing as an activity: copying the spelling of letters, letter combinations, words and their printed equivalents; copying or writing out words based on their grouping according to a certain graphic or spelling feature.

2. Exercises aimed at the formation of lexical and grammatical knowledge and skills and carried out with the help of writing (writing is a means of learning here); written performance of lexical and grammatical training exercises for substitution, sentence completion, etc.; setting questions using certain lexical and grammatical material.

3. Written exercises that serve as a means of developing other types of speech activity (writing out quotations from the text to proposed or independently compiled abstracts; brief written transmission of the text content, for example: in the form of a detailed answer to this question, etc.) [7, p. 146].

There is also a fourth type of exercises that go beyond this canon, but perfectly complement and harmoniously fit into the teaching of writing. These exercises are aimed at developing creative abilities. Creative abilities are the ability to be surprised and cognize, the ability to find solutions in non-standard

situations and the ability to deeply understand one's experience [2, p. 304]. In order for these abilities to positively influence the process of learning written English, it is important for the teacher to find such tasks that would help develop the mechanisms of creativity. The use of game techniques by teachers forms a positive motivation for children to learn. The use of the gaming method in the organization of educational activities is interesting and effective for students. To form the writing skill, the teacher can use such game techniques as: crosswords, puzzles, chainwords. With the help of these techniques, such mechanisms of creativity are developed as: fluency of thought, flexibility and originality, as well as curiosity [1, p. 203]. When preparing for creative projects, students necessarily develop writing skills, because the project implies the presence of visual material, a description of various information, a social survey, interviews, writing out various facts and their design, making up their opinions, reasoning. Exercises implement a wide variety of learning techniques, create favorable conditions for the development of speech skills and abilities in a foreign language. The importance of the exercise system is that it ensures the organization of the learning process and the organization of the learning process. It is necessary not only to know the methodological characteristics of the exercises, but also to be able to select the most appropriate ones

The results of the study. In the course of the study, a system of lessons was developed in order to form grammatical skills in English for secondary school students, consisting of three stages.

The first stage is a questionnaire and a conversation with teachers of a foreign language (English) who teach in schools in Yalta (8 people). A conversation with teachers and students revealed the degree of interest of students in learning a foreign language through the use of computer technology. When developing the program, we took into account:

- 1) the duration of the use of computer technology in the lesson;
- 2) authenticity of speech;
- 3) compliance with software requirements.

The second stage (practical) is teaching English in an experimental group using computer technologies. During the experiment, YouTube, Native-English, Lingualo services were used to provide new knowledge, as well as visibility using a smart board. A series of lessons was conducted based on the program presented in the textbook "Spotlight" for grade 6 - Module 6 and Module 7. The main means of explaining the new material were videos from the YouTube

service and explanations in the rules on the sites lingualeo.com and native-english.ru . In the last lesson, online testing was conducted on the website native-english.ru .

The third stage is the control of the results obtained during the experiment.

Three methods were used:

- the method of frontal verification (in the form of a frontal oral survey);
- the method of individual verification (control testing);
- the method of collective verification (work at the blackboard).

Thus, the survey in the control group showed that during the period of the experiment, the students did not clearly formulate the rule, operate with terms or explain why this particular rule is used in this case. The students of the experimental group became more active in the discussion, stopped "sitting out" during the survey, and more often gave correct answers, both in the frontal and in the individual survey. In the last lesson, an individual test was conducted. These tasks were performed by students of both the control and experimental groups online using the resources of the Native-English website. The results in the experimental group were significantly better.

Based on the results obtained, it can be argued that the use of computer technology makes learning attractive and really helps to individualize learning, monitor and summarize learning on a particular topic.

Conclusion. The use of computer technologies in teaching allows you to form a positive attitude to learning through the creation of a situation of success; it is an imitation of live communication by using graphic and audiovisual learning tools; it is successfully used in the process of studying regional studies; it provides information in a colorfully designed, using animation effects, in the form of text, diagrams, graphics, drawings. There is a wide variety of modern multimedia programs where you can find enough exercises for students of all ages and different levels of knowledge. The most effective and interesting are creative tasks, as they help to make the process of learning foreign language writing more interesting and simple for students, and help to teach writing more effectively.

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